

STRUCTURE MANAGEMENT IN THE COLLABORATIVE MULTIMEDIA EDITING SYSTEM IRIS

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ABSTRACT

Structure management within collaborative editing systems is an important feature when the editable documents consist of multimedia contents. This becomes even more interesting when the interface between a media-independent structure editor and the media-dependent content editors should be designed.

Based on the experiences with our common modeling framework, the newly developed multiuser editor IRIS, this paper describes the design of structure editing and discusses what operations are needed for the media-independent interface of the structure editor. Furthermore, some implications of the chosen approach are shown and a number of recommendations are made for improving our framework.

Key words: collaboration, multiuser multimedia editor, structure management.

1. Introduction

An important topic within computer-supported cooperative work (CSCW) is collaborative multimedia editing. A fully-integrated CSCW-system for such documents should provide appropriate editors for various media, i.e., there is a need for “standard” text editors to manipulate conventional text units as well as editors to play or record voice, to display or create bitmaps, etc. In general, media-dependent content editors have to be provided. Document editors, on the other hand, have to deal with structure management when the editable documents consist of multimedia contents.

In the best of all worlds, a fully-integrated system should realize a media-independent structure editor, i.e., an editor that simply manipulates structure units and that does not care for implementation details of the corresponding content units. It is the goal of this paper to motivate the design of the necessary interface of a media-independent structure editor, and to discuss the operations provided as well as some implications of our common modeling framework.

After briefly reviewing some previous work in this area, we describe our chosen modeling approach of structure management in Sect. 2. Based on the experience with our newly developed multiuser editor IRIS, we firstly describe the underlying specific logical structure, a notification mechanism to achieve group awareness, and our structure views. Then, in Sect. 3, we give the concrete operations of our structure editor. Finally, Sect. 4 concludes this paper and shows some of the implications.

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2. Structure Management in IRIS

As soon as documents become more complex, pure outline-oriented multiuser editors, such as GROVE², or toolkits for simple text editing, such as DistEdit⁶ become unsuitable. Textual information must be accompanied by structural information which can be used to define logical positions and regions in the document. These positions and regions are a necessary basis to notify the user about where other users are working. The Collaborative Editing System (CES)³ is one of the first shared editors that distinguishes between textual and structural information. The Collaborative Annotator⁸ is a multiuser document review tool where the Office Document Architecture (ODA)⁴ is seen as a potential candidate for supporting electronic document exchange. Minör gives a comparison between text-oriented and structure-oriented editors and presents an overview of existing environments¹¹.

In a multimedia environment it is even more important to separate the structure from the content. Only a media-independent structure can support a common media-independent functionality for coordination of collaborative editing operations. MultimETH⁹ is one of the relevant approaches that realize the ODA standard for their management structure. MultimETH collaboratively creates, edits and manages multimedia documents consisting of a number of structural elements, e.g., title, headings, chapters, sections, and whatsoever. The structural elements have a hierarchical relationship and a particular content, e.g., text, graphic, or bitmap.

IRIS is a new collaborative editor that distinguishes between multimedia document contents and a logical document structure. The document structure is used both for notification about collaborative activities and to separate content parts of different media. In contrast to MultimETH, IRIS has a fully-replicated architecture, i.e., contents, structure and editors are distributed among all *active* users, i.e., users that work at the same time. Synchronization of accesses is achieved using a dynamic voting scheme¹. It uses implicit coordination for basic editing of contents using dedicated media-dependent content editors as well as structure editing using a sophisticated common structure editor. It is noteworthy to point out that IRIS is designed for version management and history handling where a history tree is maintained for both, the contents and structure information, respectively. Based on an analysis of interviews with authors who have written documents together, Posner and Baecker¹⁴ stated that, with several individuals working on the same document, it is important to be able to quickly discover what changes were made, who made them, and when they were made. Therefore, our fine-grained versions are attributed to satisfy the above given requirements.

Before we give more details on structure operations and versioning in Sect. 3., this section describes the basic design of our editor and the logical structure used to manage the multimedia documents. It is shown how we present the structure to the user and how we allow for structure manipulation. Finally, it is discussed where the multimedia character of the document content influences the interfaces of the structure and content editors. It will become clear that it is possible to develop a media-independent interface.

Note that we are only concerned with a logical hierarchical structure of the document. Usually, there are a lot of other relations between content parts of a document. These include spatial and time constraints for presentation as well as content dependencies. All of these non-structural relations are not included in our model, however, they could easily be added. If they are present, they should be respected by the editor in a way corresponding to their specific semantics. As an example, content dependencies should impose reordering restrictions during structure editing. This aspect is not discussed further in this paper.

2.1. Collaborative Editing in IRIS

Fig. 1 shows our modularized editor with an operation layer on top of a data layer.

Fig. 1. Structure of the collaborative editor IRIS.

The content information is the actual content of the document. It corresponds to the document in a single user editor.

The structural information is an “explicit” document structure. It is seen and manipulated by the users. It is used by the editor mainly to give the users a compact view of the actions of users in the document. Both the structural information and the

content information also have an “implicit structure” only seen by the editor. It is used by the editor in the usual way to coordinate updates of this information. For the implicit structure, a sequence of individually lockable records is sufficient. The explicit structure should be multi-level (like a document structure with chapters, sections, subsections, paragraphs, appendices, headings, footnotes, figures and tables) to allow *logical* views of different grain in different parts of the document and to associate content with structural elements. To be more precise, we do not cope with a *layout* view that associates content with structural elements relating to presentation media, such as pages or areas within a particular page. Instead, we only need the structure to describe the document as seen by the user when it is edited. The explicit structure can be used in three principal ways. First, to inform the user about actions performed on the document, second, to coordinate the actions performed on the document on a higher level, and finally, to support actions of a single user, like positioning in the document. In all three cases the structure is used to identify parts of or positions in the document.

The history information holds previous versions of the document. Furthermore, it stores the activities of users who have already left the editing session. It enables active users to identify past modifications and to recognize “historic” work on the document at all.

The static user information can be stored in a common database. The entries cover phone numbers, Email addresses, or even bitmap photographs of the individual users of the system. All information can be displayed in a special window to allow for direct user interaction (voice, messages, etc.) or simply for “nicer” cooperation (photograph). The latter approach has been successfully implemented in GROVE. Predefined messages, such as “please free your locked section”, can be sent to the user who has locked a section.

The module of basic editing contains all the functionality which only uses and changes the content information. Thus, it is equivalent to the media-dependent functionality of a single user editor.

The document structure normally evolves during the existence of the document. Thus, analogous to the basic editing of the contents, the editor must allow editing of the document structure. This functionality is separated from basic editing because the editing operations for the document structure differ from those for the contents and, most importantly, are media-independent. Typical operations are: defining a new part, removing an existing part, and moving/copying a part to another position in the structure. It is interesting to note that copying makes it necessary to connect the content information module to the structure editing module. Both the basic editing module and the structure editing module must coordinate concurrent updates. This is a typical implicit coordination that is done by the editor itself.

Besides an implicit way of hidden coordination, explicit coordination operations should be provided at the user level. This module contains all functionality for explicit coordination. Typical cases are the explicit locking of a document part by a user, a request to unlock a part, or even requesting another user to work on a part. The locks in this module may either be “soft”, i.e., they are only shown to the other users,

or “hard”, i.e., the editor guarantees the exclusive access to a locked part.

The dynamic profile contains all functions that give one user information about the actions of the other users, e.g., joining the editing session, changing a certain document part or locking a document part. The module uses the document structure as a basis to show which document parts are involved. The dynamic profile is also involved in displaying “historic” changes.

The document structure can be used for other purposes as well, which need not have coordination aspects. Examples of other features are positioning on the beginning/end of a document part or defining the content of a part to be a region to which a basic editing function like “delete” should be applied.

2.2. *Specific Logical Structure*

In the following we solely focus on structure editing and the operations needed to perform well. In general, the document structure separates the document into parts. Structure editing allows the user to select parts for deletion, to select positions for creating new parts or moving/copying existing parts, and to specify or change part identifiers.

In order to create a system that can be used effectively, we emphasize electronic document standards, such as the Standard Generalized Markup Language (SGML)⁵ or the Office Document Architecture (ODA)⁴. SGML contains a syntax to exchange document structures without providing an explicit definition of the semantics of such structures. Consequently, SGML-based systems need additional agreements between the corresponding sites. ODA, on the other hand, defines schemes to describe data structures as well as rules for the document layout using standardized semantics. Furthermore, a syntax for the interchange of this information is given.

In IRIS we chose the logical structure to have the form of the *specific logical structure* from ODA. Since we use the structure mainly to access the document content during editing, the simple tree structure of ODA is sufficient for our purpose. We prefer it over hypermedia structures because of its easy visualizability. The visualization of the structure in our so-called “structure views” (see Sect. 2.4.) is crucial for the functionality of interactive structure manipulation.

Here we briefly describe the relevant parts of the ODA specific logical structure. It forms a tree of objects that are typed in four ways. First, the document logical root is the root of the tree. Second, the content portions are contiguous parts of the document content whereas the basic logical objects are nodes with only content portions as subnodes. Finally, there are composite logical objects as inner nodes with no content portions as subnodes.

Every object has a number. The sequence of numbers on the path from the document logical root to an object must identify the object uniquely and is called its *object identifier*. Every object which is not a content portion may have a *user visible name*, which is an arbitrary string like “function model” or “Chapter 1” as shown in Fig. 2. Here we show the different document parts of the entire IRIS project documentation where each phase has its own subdocumental environment.

Fig. 2. Part of the explicit structure of the IRIS project documentation.

Names are usually defined or changed by the users, but they may also be generated automatically. For the subnodes of every node a sequential order is defined which may be different from the order of their identifying numbers. Note that this induces a sequential order on the set of all content portions, and, most importantly, makes a content portion an ideal candidate for an update unit, i.e., our implicit coordination within our dynamic voting scheme has a content portion as granularity for both, locking and notification.

2.3. Notification

The content portions together are the document content, which in IRIS is stored separately from the structure. Content portions are multimedia containers of information, i.e., in a multimedia document they may correspond to a single text paragraph, a voice recording, or an animation sequence, etc.

The leaves of the explicit structure tree contain links to the corresponding content portions. These links are attributed. The attributes are used in two ways. First, the attribute of the link reflects the kind of content and gives a strong hint to what content editor should be used to display or manipulate the content portion. Second, the attributes of links to the content portions can be used for notification which is an essential feature of a collaborative editing system. Notification is needed to realize group awareness. Among others, the state, the creation time, and the authorship of the editable material are reported. Recall that the replicated nature of IRIS may lead to update delays and local inconsistencies due to network partitionings. Globally, of course, the entire document is consistent through the use of our voting scheme. The state notification helps to detect such irregularities. Fig. 3 shows a screenshot of a (text-) content editing module as seen by user “maekioe”. At present, “maekioe”

edits the second paragraph while user "kochm" remotely edits the third paragraph. This information together with the current user set which is displayed in the bottom line make the users aware of each other.

Thu Feb 4 16:09	Der Teilnehmer braucht sich um die Einteilung in Bereiche nicht zu k"ummern, die Dokumentstruktur wird mit jeder Text"anderung nach Bedarf angepa"st.
maekioe	Ist der Benutzer alleiniger Teilnehmer, so arbeitet er mit dem Verteilten Editor nahezu genauso wie mit einem herk"ommlichen Einbenutzereditor. Bei mehreren Teilnehmern stellt sich heraus, da"s Editorkommandos eine ver"anderte Semantik erhalten. Dies ist auch der Hauptgrund da"ur, da"s es sich hier kaum lohnt einen herk"ommlichen Einbenutzereditor zu einem mehrbenutzertauglichen Editor umzuschreiben.
locked by kochm	Die gebr"auchlichsten, kritischen Editorkommandos, wie {em Sichern}, {em Ersetzen}, {em L"oschen}, {em Zur"ucknehmen} und andere, werden auf ihre Mehrbenutzertauglichkeit untersucht, verschiedene Vorgehensweisen angesprochen und Sperrstrategien werden entwickelt.
Thu Feb 4 16:09	In einer Fallstudie wurden einige der entwickelten Vorgehensweisen realisiert. Der Dokumenttext und Kopien im Netz werden von einer Zugriffsschicht verwaltet, die auch die Kommunikation zwischen den Rechnern erledigt. Die Benutzerschnittstelle h"alt nur die f"ur den momentanen Gebrauch erforderlichen Daten bei sich. Diese m"ussen mit der lokalen Kopie konsistent gehalten werden, weshalb Bereiche zumeist "uber einen benachbarten Bereich referenziert
neumann kochm neumann maekioe	

Fig. 3. Notification during collaborative text editing.

2.4. Structure Views

The explicit structure itself consists of the tree without the content portions. This type of structure allows for the necessary flexibility and frees the design of our structure editor from details of the particular multimedia implementation of the content portions. A tree node, therefore, can describe or represent a paragraph, a chapter, a sequence of voice recordings, animation sequences, a declaration in a program source, a whole multimedia document or even a set of such documents.

The explicit structure is presented to the user in the form of one or more *structure views*. A structure view depicts one object from the structure in an iconic way. The object may be the logical root, or a basic or composite logical object, but in no case a content portion. The concrete appearance is a rectangular space on the screen.

Additionally, the icon for an object may display one or more of the following items that are individually and interactively configurable by the user: the identifying number, the user visible name, or the sequence of iconic representations of all subordinate objects in their sequential order provided it is no basic logical object. Note that a structure view never displays parts of the document contents. Thus it is independent

of the contents kinds used in the multimedia document.

Fig. 4 depicts two possible structure views of the node named “design phase” from the structure in Fig. 2.

Structure views are used as the main content-independent and media-independent user interface of IRIS. A structure view may depict the current situation, or it may show the structure of an already obsolete version. It may give a view of the whole document or of a certain part of it. It can be used by itself to navigate through the multimedia document and to change the structure, thus it is the single user interface to the structure editor.

Additionally, the media-dependent content editors may use structure views as input and output medium for operations like (structure relative) positioning or notification. In order to facilitate this feature, the content editors must have access to a standard interface of the structure views. The interface allows the reaction to input events via a structure view (like selecting a document part) and several functions for output via a structure view (like marking a document part or pointing to it).

Basically, input and output via structure views are relative to whole structure objects, as for the structure editing functions. However, on icons for basic logical objects this could be extended by mapping the rectangular icon region in a medium-dependent way to the extent of the content. As an example, the horizontal dimension could represent the character position in a text, whereas it represents time for audio or video contents. In this paper we do not further investigate this idea.

3. Structure Operations

The operation interface of the structure editor is independent of the particular attributes of the content portions, especially independent of their concrete media. In contrast to that, of course, the implementation of the operations and their concrete effects on the data are strongly influenced by the media used.

In the remainder, we focus on the independent parts of the structure editor. These parts form the main interface to the multimedia document. Content-dependent parts may be activated in a uniform way as subtasks.

Fig. 4: Two structure views of node “design phase”.

3.1. Access Coordination for the Structural Information

As we said above, the basic editing uses content portions as update units. All content portions are independent of each other and may be locked separately (cf. Fig. 3). For the structural information we want to use similar coordination mechanisms, thus we need update units in the logical structure as well. As structure editing may change any object in the tree structure we decided that **any** object may be an update unit.

This implies an important difference to the case for the contents. Since a structure object may be part of another structure object, structure update units may not be locked independently of each other. The locking mechanism must be extended to prevent locking of an object whenever a part of it is locked. The content portions are treated as part of the corresponding basic logical object, thus locking a structure object may be prevented by a lock on a content portion that belongs to the structure object.

The extended locking mechanism is used with the same strategies and voting mechanisms as in the coordination of the content information, i.e., using version numbers for structure objects and implicit coordination (locks) within our dynamic voting scheme. This scheme is implemented by Koch⁷.

3.2. Structure Browsing

An important part of the interaction with structure views is to create and configure structure views interactively. Upon the start of IRIS on a certain document, a single structure view for the logical root is created automatically. It does not show any subnodes.

An existing structure view can be configured in the following general way. A depicted object may be selected and the display of its user visible name, the object index or the subobjects may be enabled or disabled independently. Thus a structure view may be configured to show some parts in detail while hiding other parts.

Additionally, new structure views may be created by selecting an object depicted by an existing structure view. If this object is not the logical root, the new structure view only gives access to a part of the document. In this way the user can maintain several different views of the document, e.g., an overall view of the document as a whole and a detailed view of the part he is working on.

At any time a structure view may be closed. When the last view on a document is closed, the user has finished his editing session for this document.

3.3. Structure Editing

There are five operations which change the structure. All of them may be initiated in the usual way using a structure view, i.e., by selecting or dragging objects in the view. The operations are:

- *insert*: A new logical object is created as subobject of the selected object. If the selected object was a basic logical object it is changed into a composite logical

object. This is only possible if no content portion was defined for it. The user may give a name to the new object.

- *delete*: The selected logical object is deleted. This includes the deletion of all subobjects.
- *move*: The selected logical object is moved from its current superobject to another superobject. As for the insert operation, the target object must not be a basic logical object with a defined content portion.
- *copy*: Copy the selected logical object to another (or the same) superobject. This implies copying all subobjects. As for the insert operation, the target object must not be a basic logical object with a defined content portion. The copy has the same name, however a new number is created and thus it (and all its subobject) have a new index.
- *rename*: Change the user visible name of the selected object.

The requirement that the target object of the operations insert, move, and copy may not have a defined content is a consequence of the ODA structure. No object may have both subobjects and a content portion. It is easy to convert a basic logical object with an empty content portion to a composite logical object by removing the content portion. If a non-empty content portion has to be retained in the target object, it must be manually converted to a subobject using the structure editing operations.

All structure editing operations implicitly lock the involved structure objects using the dynamic voting mechanism, and at least the current majority of the structure replicas is updated in the usual way. All local structure views as well as all available (again, at least the current majority!) remotely displayed structure views are updated to show the changes, if necessary.

3.4. Versioning

Versioning is done in accordance with two principles:

- *implicit versioning*: every “change” of a document part introduces a new version of this part,
- *hierarchical versioning*: every version change of a subpart implies a version change of the superpart.

The versioning of the content portions is implemented by the content editors in charge. In particular, they define the granularity of a “change” to a content portion. Every content portion has its own version independent of those of other content portions.

The versioning of the structure is implemented by the structure editor. Every operation described in Sect. 3.3. is considered to be a “change”. This results in a relatively fine-grained version history. To keep it manageable for the user, every version is given attributes, such as the time of its existence, or the user who did the change that created this version.

The interface that gives access to older versions of the document are structure views, too. Every structure view has an associated control panel to select the version it should display. This function allows associative access to versions via its attributes (like selecting the last version created by the user himself) as well as stepping through the single versions. A structure view may be in one of two states. Either it shows a “current” version or it shows an “old” version. In the first case, no version exists after that which is shown. Upon any version change of the corresponding document part, the view is updated if necessary. Thus the view keeps track of the changes and always shows the current version. In the second case, the view always shows the version the user selected in it. If a changing operation is initiated from a structure view showing an old version, a new offspring of that version is created. This is possible for any version either using structure operations or changing a content portion. Thus in general the version history of a document is a version tree. A similar sort of revision by versioning is also supported in the PREP editor¹³.

Fig. 5 shows a possible version tree of a document together with some attributes. It mirrors the following scenario. In an empty document, first, a new logical object is inserted by, let us say, Uwe. He then inserted another logical object, changed the user visible name of a selected object, and deleted some logical object. All resulting versions are attributed, i.e., the creator’s name, the creation time, and an version identifier are stored together with the new version. For example, on December 24th, 1992, 12:04, Uwe created Version 7.0 by deleting a logical object. Later, on January 1st, 1993, 08:58, Gunnar inserted a logical object into an old version, hence creating Version 1.1, and so forth.

It is planned to extend the versioning mechanism described here by “undo/redo” functions which allow the selective undoing/redoing of intermediate steps and by an intelligent “diffing” function that can be used to show the differences between arbitrary versions. Prakash and Knister¹⁵ as well as Neuwirth *et al.*¹², respectively, have already discussed some of the implications. Research, however, is still needed to implement the appropriate human interfaces.

3.5. Activating Content-Dependent Editor Parts

The last kind of operations initiated with the help of structure views is the starting of content-dependent subtasks. IRIS distinguishes two kinds of subtasks: browsers and editors. A *content browser* can be used to output certain kinds of content, however it cannot change content portions. A *content editor* need not necessarily output the content portions, however, it can be used to change content portions of a certain kind. The reason for this separation lies in the variety of content kinds which are possible in a multimedia document. For plain text it is easy to implement an interactive editor that subsumes the features of a browser. For other content kinds, like voice recordings, it may be more adequate to do input and output in separate tools.

A content depending subtask is started on a structure object selected in a structure view. The structure view remains associated to the subtask until it is closed and can be used as additional input/output medium (e.g., for positioning, cf. Sect. 2.4.). The

Fig. 5. Version tree of a document.

subtask allows access to all content portions of the structure object, usually using the sequential order induced on the portions by the structure.

A content editor may be restricted to do changes only in existing basic logical objects and do not change the structure. However, a more user-friendly content editor will additionally offer functions that include structure changes as well. An example is the *splitting* of a basic logical object at a certain position in its content portion. The content editor uses an internal interface to the structure editing operations introduced in Sect. 3.3. to implement functions of this kind.

A content-dependent subtask can only handle content portions of one or some kinds. However, it must contain a simple default mechanism to output content portions of other kinds, because all kinds may appear in the selected structure object. For example, a subtask which handles plain text could output other content portions by printing their name and kind, a bitmap handler could use a box showing name and kind, and a voice handler could use a special acoustic signal.

This framework allows a wide variety of content subtasks. Simple subtasks handle only one content kind and simply provide input or output separately. Other subtasks may allow the interactive editing of several contents kinds like text, bitmaps, and video sequences. By providing new and more sophisticated subtasks, IRIS may be incrementally extended to handle more kinds of contents and to offer more manipulation functions to the user.

4. Conclusion

In this paper we proposed a uniform framework for collaborative multimedia editing, version control, and most importantly, structure manipulation. With our structure views the user is relieved from the burden of positioning in unstructured documents, and can then concentrate on the editing process. Clicking on the mouse within a structure view, for instance, results in displaying the substructure view in a predefined depth or, if a leaf is clicked on, the correct content editor is started in order to display the linked content portion. The attributes of links to the content portions are used for notification, i.e., for group awareness in our collaborative editing system. Moreover, we showed that the definition of a concise interface between a media-independent structure editor and the media-dependent content editors is possible. As far as different media is concerned, it allows for quite easy extension to a integrated system because the general framework can be augmented by a variety of content editors or content browsers provided they realize the concise interface definition.

Currently, structure management in IRIS is enhanced with all mechanisms to deal with multimedia content portions. It is implemented in ANSI-C and runs on our HP-workstation cluster operating HPUNIX V8.07. The ISIS toolkit V3.0 is used to provide the multicast feature. The graphical interface has been written using the InterViews 3.01 software package. Mäkiö has written a first content editor for text that realizes our interface, “vi”-functionality, and some specific notification mechanisms¹⁰.

This limited version is available on request. Work is in progress in the following areas.

- full ODA-style structures;
- multimedia content portions with spatial and time constraints for presentation as well as content dependencies;
- version and history handling together with presentation of version diff's;
- asynchronous mode of operation.¹⁶

We expect to provide an enhanced beta-version by the end of 1993 or shortly thereafter.

5. Acknowledgments

We are grateful to Anke Mäkiö and Michael Koch for implementing parts of the first version of IRIS. We wish to thank Prof. J.H. Schlichter for stimulating discussions and constructive comments on earlier versions of this paper.

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